

Cytological endometritis diagnosis in primiparous versus multiparous dairy cows

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Supplemental Table S1: information about the farms participated in the study. All animals in the study were Israeli Holstein–Friesian cows.

Farm	Geographic location¹	n²	Parity³	Annual milk yield (kg)⁴
Nahshonim	Central Israel (32°06'N, 34°95'E)	98	2.44±0.15 (1-6)	11,492
Be'erot Yitshak	Central Israel (32°02'N, 34°54'E)	146	2.47±0.13 (1-9)	12,539
Zikim	Southern Israel (31°61'N, 34°52'E)	59	2.42±0.18 (1-5)	12,486
Gvar'am	Southern Israel (31°59'N, 34°61'E)	60	2.25±0.21 (1-10)	12,396
Dorot	Southern Israel (31°50'N, 34°65'E)	52	2.65±0.21 (1-6)	12,925

¹Farms locations are presented as area (latitude, longitude)

²Number of cows included from each farm

³Mean±SEM (range)

⁴Mean annual milk yield per cow

Supplemental Table S2: voluntary waiting periods in the farms participated in the study by calendar months.

Voluntary waiting period (DIM¹)										
Farm	Nahshonim		Be'erot Yitshak		Zikim		Gvar'am		Dorot	
Month	Primi ²	Multi ³								
January	100	100	80	70	110	110	150	120	100	100
February	100	100	130	120	110	110	150	120	100	100
Mars	100	100	130	120	100	100	150	120	95	95
April	70	60	130	120	80	80	150	120	80	75
May	70	60	130	120	80	80	90	80	75	70
June	70	60	130	120	80	80	90	80	70	60
July	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	70	60
August	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	70	65
September	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	75	70
October	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	80	80
November	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	90	90
December	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	100	100

¹Days in milk

²Primiparous cows

³Multiparous cows

Supplemental Table S3: Periparturient diseases. The prevalence of ketosis, metritis, retained fetal membranes, as well as body condition score (at 40-60DIM) are presented for all cows in the study. Cows were defined as CEM positive by PMN% threshold of $\geq 4\%$ at 35 ± 5 DIM (E35), and at 65 ± 5 DIM (E65). Differences between CEM positive (CEM+) and CEM negative (CEM-) cows were analyzed by Chi-square test.

	All cows E35				All cows E65			
	All	CEM +	CEM-	χ^2 -test P value	All	CEM+	CEM-	χ^2 -test P value
Ketosis	36.1% (140/388)	40.7% (57/140)	33.5% (83/248)	0.1877	35.8% (135/377)	39.4% (41/104)	34.4% (94/273)	0.4335
Metritis	46.6% (180/386)	55.0% (77/140)	41.9% (103/246)	0.0173	45.6% (171/375)	55.3% (57/103)	41.9% (114/272)	0.0268
RFM¹	3.6% (14/386)	2.9% (4/140)	4.1% (10/246)	0.7436	3.7% (14/375)	5.8% (6/103)	2.9% (8/272)	0.3126
BCS²								
<2.5	11.4% (43/376)	14.1% (19/135)	10.0% (24/241)	0.3129	11.5% (42/366)	13% (13/100)	10.9% (29/266)	0.6849
2.5-3.5	87.0% (327/376)	85.2% (115/135)	88.0% (212/241)		87.2% (319/366)	85.0% (85/100)	88.0% (234/266)	
>3.5	1.6% (6/376)	0.7% (1/135)	2.1% (5/241)		1.4% (5/366)	2.0% (2/100)	1.1% (3/266)	

¹ Retained fetal membranes

² Body condition score

Supplemental Table S4: Periparturient diseases in primiparous and multiparous cows. The prevalence of ketosis, metritis, retained fetal membranes (RFM), as well as body condition score (at 40-60DIM) are presented for primiparous (left) and multiparous (right) cows independently. Primiparous cows were defined as CEM positive by PMN% threshold of $\geq 7\%$ at 35 ± 5 DIM (E35); multiparous cows defined as CEM positive by PMN% threshold of $\geq 4\%$ at 65 ± 5 DIM (E65). Differences between CEM positive (CEM+) and CEM negative (CEM-) cows were analyzed by Chi-square test.

	Primiparous cows (E35)				Multiparous cows (E65)			
	All	CEM+	CEM-	χ^2 -test P value	All	CEM+	CEM-	χ^2 -test P value
Ketosis	33.1% (44/133)	45.9% (17/37)	28.1% (27/96)	0.0798	38% (92/242)	44.9% (31/69)	35.3% (61/173)	0.2106
Metritis	49.6% (66/133)	64.9% (24/37)	43.8% (42/96)	0.0467	45.4% (109/240)	57.4% (39/68)	40.7% (70/172)	0.0284
RFM¹	1.5% (2/133)	0% (0/37)	2.1% (2/96)	0.9286	5% (12/240)	7.4% (5/68)	4.1% (7/172)	0.4697
BCS²								
<2.5	6.9% (9/130)	2.8% (1/36)	8.5% (8/94)	0.2708	14.6% (34/233)	18.2% (12/66)	13.2% (22/167)	0.4790
2.5-3.5	90.8% (118/130)	97.2% (35/36)	88.3% (83/94)		84.5% (197/233)	80.3% (53/66)	86.2% (144/167)	
>3.5	2.3% (3/130)	0% (0/36)	3.2% (3/94)		0.9% (2/233)	1.5% (1/66)	0.6% (1/167)	

¹ Retained fetal membranes

² Body condition score